

Peptides after SGPS and MaxQuant(203)	803 Peptides	Total Unique peptides (906)	82 Confident Peptides
GGQVPINTNSSPDDQIGYYRR	AAITILDGISQYSLR	AAITILDGISQYSLR	ADEQALPQR
YLGTPPEAGLPYGANK	AAIVLQLPQGTTLPK	AAIVLQLPQGTTLPK	ASANLAATK
AYNVTQAFGR	AALALLLLDR	AALALLLLDR	AYETQALPQR
RGPEQTQGNFGDQELIR	AALALLLLDRLNQLESK	AALALLLLDRLNQLESK	AYNVTQAFGR
AGGNYNYRYR	AALLADKFPVLHDIGNPK	AALLADKFPVLHDIGNPK	CDIKDLPK
CEFQFCNDPFLDVYYHKNNK	ACPLIAAVITR	ACPLIAAVITR	DDKDPNFKDQVILLNK
MADSNGTVEELKK	ACVEEVTTLLEETK	ACVEEVTTLLEETK	DDQIGYYR
RPQGLPNNTASWFTALTQHGK	ADEQALPQR	ADEQALPQR	DGIIWVATEGALNTPK
KQQTVTLLPAADLDDFSK	ADEQALPQRQ	ADEQALPQRQ	DGIIWVATEGALNTPKG
ITFVEPSDSTGSNQNGER	ADEQALPQRQK	ADEQALPQRQK	DRLNQLESK
ITFVGPSDSTDSNQNGER	ADEQALPQRQKK	ADEQALPQRQKK	EITVATSR
IGMEVTPSGTWLTYTGAIK	ADSNGTITVEELK	ADSNGTITVEELK	FDNPVLPFNDGVYFASTEK
MAGNGGDAALALLLLDR	ADSNGTITVEELKK	ADSNGTITVEELKK	FNGIGVTQNVLYENQK
NKCINFNFLGTGTGVLTESNKK	AENVTGLFK	AENVTGLFK	GEGVPINTNSSPDDQIGYYR
ADEQALPQR	AFDIYNDK	AFDIYNDK	GFQPTNGVGYQPYR
ASANLAATK	AFDIYNDKVAGFAK	AFDIYNDKVAGFAK	GFYAEGSR
CDIKDLPK	AFQLTPIAVQMTK	AFQLTPIAVQMTK	GGDAALALLLLDR
CYGVSPTK	AFQLTPIAVQMTKLATTEELPDEFVWTVK	AFQLTPIAVQMTKLATTEELPDEFVWTVK	GIWVATEGALNTPK
EIDRLNEVAK	AGEAANFCALILAYCNK	AGEAANFCALILAYCNK	GPEQTQGNFGDQELIR
EINRLNEVAK	AGGTTEMLAK	AGGTTEMLAK	GPEQTQGNFGDQELTR
EITVATSR	AGNATEVPANSTVLSFCFAVDAAK	AGNATEVPANSTVLSFCFAVDAAK	GGQVPINTNSSPDDQIGY
ELTVATSR	AGNGGDAALALLLLDR	AGNGGDAALALLLLDR	GGQVPINTNSSPDDQIGYYR
GFYAEGSR	AGNGGDAALALLLLDRLNQLESK	AGNGGDAALALLLLDRLNQLESK	GGQVPINTNSSR
HTPINLVR	AISSVLNDILSR	AISSVLNDILSR	HWPQIAQFAPSASAFF
IAGHHLGR	AIVSTIQR	AIVSTIQR	HWPQIAQFAPSASAFFGMSR
ICASHQTQTN SPR	ALNDFSNSGSDVLYQPPQTSITS AVLQ	ALNDFSNSGSDVLYQPPQTSITS AVLQ	IAGHHLGR
KADEQALPQR	ALNDFSNSGSDVLYQPPQTSITS AVLQSGFR	ALNDFSNSGSDVLYQPPQTSITS AVLQSGFR	IGMEVTPSGTWLTYTGAIK
KANETQALPQR	ALNLGETFVTHSK	ALNLGETFVTHSK	IWVATEGALNTPK
KKADEQALPQR	ALTAESHVDTDLTKPYIK	ALTAESHVDTDLTKPYIK	ITFGG PSDSTGSNQDGER
LDDKDPNFK	ALTGIAVEQDK	ALTGIAVEQDK	ITFGG PSDSTGSNQNGER
MSECVLGQSK	ALTGIAVEQDKNTQEVFAQVK	ALTGIAVEQDKNTQEVFAQVK	ITFGG PSDSTGSNQNGGAR
NNISWMESE	ALTQHGKEDLK	ALTQHGKEDLK	KADEQALPQR
QLQQSMSSADSTQA	ANNAIVLQLPQGTTLPK	ANNAIVLQLPQGTTLPK	KAYETQALPQR
SNLKPFER	APSASAFFGMSR	APSASAFFGMSR	KKADEQALPQR
TFGAGAAL	ASANIGCNHTGVVGESEGLNDNLLEILQK	ASANIGCNHTGVVGESEGLNDNLLEILQK	KQQTVTLLPAADLDDFSK
TFPPTPEK	ASANLAATK	ASANLAATK	KSNLKPFER

TNQFNSAIGK	ASCTLSEQLDFIDTK	ASCTLSEQLDFIDTK	LDDKDPNFK
CDIKNLPK	ASCTLSEQLDFIDTKR	ASCTLSEQLDFIDTKR	LDDKDPNFKDQVILLNK
EIDRLNQVAK	ASMPPTIAK	ASMPPTIAK	LGSPLSLNMAR
GVYYPDK	ASWFTALTQH GK	ASWFTALTQH GK	LGTGPEAGLPYGANK
LDDKNPNFK	ASWFTALTQH GKEDLK	ASWFTALTQH GKEDLK	LIANQFNSAIGK
QLQQSMSSSDSTQA	ASYQTQTN SPR	ASYQTQTN SPR	LQDVVNQNAQALNTLVK
RVDFCGK	ATCEFCGTENLTK	ATCEFCGTENLTK	LQSLQTYVTQQLIR
DGIIWVATEGALNTPK	ATNNAMQVESDDYIATNGPLK	ATNNAMQVESDDYIATNGPLK	LYTGTAIK
DGIIWVATEGALNTPKG	AVDCALDPLSETK	AVDCALDPLSETK	LVDPQIQLAVTR
GIIWVATEGALNTPK	AVFISPYNSQNAVASK	AVFISPYNSQNAVASK	MAGDGGDAALALLLLDR
IIVWATEGALNTPK	AVGACVLCNSQTSLR	AVGACVLCNSQTSLR	MAGNGGDAALALLLLDR
IWVATEGALNTPK	AYKDYLASGGQPITNCVK	AYKDYLASGGQPITNCVK	MAGNGGDAALALLLLDRLNQLESK
MAGNGCDAALALLLLNR	AYNVTQAFGR	AYNVTQAFGR	MSECVLGQSK
VATEGALNTPK	AYNVTQAFGRR	AYNVTQAFGRR	NPANNAAIVQLPQGTTLPK
WVATEGALNTPK	CAGSTFISDEVAR	CAGSTFISDEVAR	NPANNAAIVLQLPQGT
DGILWVATEGALNTPK	CDHCGETSWQTGDFVK	CDHCGETSWQTGDFVK	NSSPDDQIGYYR
NPANNAAIVLQLPQGTTLPK	CDIKDLPK	CDIKDLPK	NSTPGSSMGTS PAR
RPQGLPNNTASWFTALTQH GKEDLK	CDIKDLPKEITVATSR	CDIKDLPKEITVATSR	NTNSSPDDQIGYYR
ITFGG PSDSTGSNQDGER	CDLQNYGDSATLPK	CDLQNYGDSATLPK	PAADLDDFSK
HWPQIAQFAPSASAFF	CLWSTKPVETSNSFDVLK	CLWSTKPVETSNSFDVLK	PGNGCDAALALLLLDR
GQGVPIINTNSPDDQIGYYR	CPAEIVDTV SALVYDNK	CPAEIVDTV SALVYDNK	QGTDYKHWPQIAQFAPSASAFFGMSR
RPQGLPNNTASWF	CSFYEDFLEYHDV R	CSFYEDFLEYHDV R	QKRTATKAYNVTQAFGR
QQTVTLLPAADLDDFSK	CTSVVLLSVLQQLR	CTSVVLLSVLQQLR	QLQQSMSSADSTQA
RPQGLPDNTASWF	CVNFNFNGLTGTGVLTESNK	CVNFNFNGLTGTGVLTESNK	QQTVTLLPAADLDDFSK
QLPQGTTLPK	CVNFNFNGLTGTGVLTESNKK	CVNFNFNGLTGTGVLTESNKK	RGPEQTQGNFGDQELTR
SWMESEFR	CYGVSP TK	CYGVSP TK	RPQGLPNNTASW
LDDKDPNFKDQVILLNK	DAPAHISTIGVCSMTDIAK	DAPAHISTIGVCSMTDIAK	RPQGLPNNTASWF
LYTGTAIK	DAPYIVGDVVQEGVLTAVVIPTK	DAPYIVGDVVQEGVLTAVVIPTK	RPQGLPNNTASWFTALTQH GK
GPEQTQGNFGDQELIR	DAPYIVGDVVQEGVLTAVVIPTKK	DAPYIVGDVVQEGVLTAVVIPTKK	RPQGLPNNTASWFTALTQH GKEDLK
GWIFGTTLDSK	DASGKVPYCYDTNVLEGSVAYESLRPDTR	DASGKVPYCYDTNVLEGSVAYESLRPDTR	SFIEDLLFNK
ITFGG PSDSTGSNQNGER	DATPSDFVR	DATPSDFVR	SMGTSPTRMAGNGGDAALALLLLDR
WYFYLLGTGPEAGLPY	DDKDPNFKDQVILLNK	DDKDPNFKDQVILLNK	SNLKPFER
RPQGLPNNTASW	DFGGFNFSQILPDPSKPSK	DFGGFNFSQILPDPSKPSK	TALTQH GKEDLK
LTQH GKEDLK	DFMSLSEQLR	DFMSLSEQLR	TALTQH GKEDLKFP R
GQGVPIINTNSPDDQIGYY	DFMSLSEQLRK	DFMSLSEQLRK	TATKAYNVTQAFGR
LGTGPEAGLPYGANK	DFYDFAVSK	DFYDFAVSK	TQH GKEDLKFP R
MAGNGGDAALALLLLDRLNQLESK	DGCVPLNIPLTTAAK	DGCVPLNIPLTTAAK	VAGDSGFAAYS R

PAADLDDFSK	DGHVETFYPK	DGHVETFYPK	VATEGALNTPK
HWPQIAQFAPSASAF	DGIWVATEGALNTPK	DGIWVATEGALNTPK	VGGNYNYLYR
IGMEVTPSGTWLTY	DGIWVATEGALNTPKDHIGTR	DGIWVATEGALNTPKDHIGTR	VTLADAGFIK
GFYAEGSRGGSEASSR	DGIWVATEGALNTPKDHIGTRNPANNAIIVLQLPQ	DGIWVATEGALNTPKDHIGTRNPANNAIIVLQLPQGT	VYSTGSNVFQTR
RPQGLPNNTASWFTAL	DGTCGLVEVEK	DGTCGLVEVEK	WVATEGALNTPK
KSNLKPFFER	DHIGTRNPANNAIIVLQLPQGTTLPK	DHIGTRNPANNAIIVLQLPQGTTLPK	WYFYLLGTGPEAGLPYGANK
VGGNYNYLYR	DIADTTDAVR	DIADTTDAVR	YLGTGPEAGLPYGANK
LNTDHSSSDNIALLVQ	DIADTTDAVRD	DIADTTDAVRD	YYLGTGPEAGLPYGANK
WYFYLLGTGPEAGLPYGANK	DIADTTDAVRDPQ	DIADTTDAVRDPQ	
RGPEQTQGNFGDQELTR	DIADTTDAVRDPQTLEILDITPC	DIADTTDAVRDPQTLEILDITPC	
NPANNAIIVLQLPQGT	DIASDTCFANK	DIASDTCFANK	
GGDAALALLLLDR	DLGACIDCSAR	DLGACIDCSAR	
TQLPPAYTNSFTR	DLPKEITVATSR	DLPKEITVATSR	
VTLADAGFIK	DLPQGFSALEPLVDLPIGINITR	DLPQGFSALEPLVDLPIGINITR	
NTNSSPDDQIGYYR	DLSPRWYFYLLGTGPEAGLPYGANK	DLSPRWYFYLLGTGPEAGLPYGANK	
FDNPVLPFNDGVYFASTEK	DLSPRWYFYLLGTGPEAGLPYGANKDGIWVATE	DLSPRWYFYLLGTGPEAGLPYGANKDGIWVATEGALNTPK	
FLPFQQFSR	DLYDKLQFTSLEIPR	DLYDKLQFTSLEIPR	
GWIFGTTLDPK	DNSYFTEQPIDLVPNQYPNASFDNFK	DNSYFTEQPIDLVPNQYPNASFDNFK	
AGDGGDAALALLLLDR	DPNFKDQVILLNK	DPNFKDQVILLNK	
AYIVTQAFGR	DPQTLEILDITPC	DPQTLEILDITPC	
FNGIGVTQNVLYENQK	DQNNVGPVKVYPIILR	DQNNVGPVKVYPIILR	
LIANQFNSAIGK	DQVILLNK	DQVILLNK	
SSPDDQIGYYR	DQVILLNKHIDAYK	DQVILLNKHIDAYK	
HWPQIAQF	DSNGTITVEELKK	DSNGTITVEELKK	
MAGDGGDAALALLLLDRLNQLESK	DVDTDFVNEFYAYLR	DVDTDFVNEFYAYLR	
TLLPAADLDDFSK	DWSYSGQSTQLGIEFLK	DWSYSGQSTQLGIEFLK	
YYLGTGPEAGLPYGANK	DWYDFVENPDILR	DWYDFVENPDILR	
NSSPDDQIGYYR	DYLASGGQPITNCVK	DYLASGGQPITNCVK	
SMGTSPTRMAGNGGDAALALLLLDR	EAPAHVSTIGVCTMTDIAK	EAPAHVSTIGVCTMTDIAK	
HWPQIAQFAPSASAFFGMSR	EETGLLMPLKAPK	EETGLLMPLKAPK	
FPQGGVPINTNSSR	EEVKPFITESKPSVEQR	EEVKPFITESKPSVEQR	
LLDRLNQLESK	EFVFNIDGYFK	EFVFNIDGYFK	
RPQGLPNNTASWFTALTQHGKEDLKFPR	EGATTGYPQNAVVK	EGATTGYPQNAVVK	
RFDNPVLPFNDGVYFASTEK	EGFFTYICGFIQQK	EGFFTYICGFIQQK	
VQPTESIVR	EGIVWVATEGALNTPK	EGIVWVATEGALNTPK	
FTALTQHGKEDLK	EGIVWVATEGALNTPKDHIGTR	EGIVWVATEGALNTPKDHIGTR	
QQGVPINTNSSPDDQIGY	EGQINDMILSLLSK	EGQINDMILSLLSK	

GPEQTQGNFGDQELTR	EGSSVELK	EGSSVELK	
QGTDYKHWPQIAQFAPSASAFF	EGVFVSNNGTHWFTQR	EGVFVSNNGTHWFTQR	
ALALLLDR	EHEHEIAWYTER	EHEHEIAWYTER	
VAGDSGFAAYS	EIDRLNEVAK	EIDRLNEVAK	
LQDVVNQNAQALNTLVK	EIIFLEGETLPTEVLTEEVVK	EIIFLEGETLPTEVLTEEVVK	
ITFGGSDSTGNSQDGERSGAR	EITVATSR	EITVATSR	
RPQGLPNNTASWFT	EITVATSRTLSYYK	EITVATSRTLSYYK	
MAGNGGDAIAIALLLDRLNQLESK	EITVATSRTLSYYKLGASQR	EITVATSRTLSYYKLGASQR	
DDKDPNFKDQVILLNK	EKNINIVGDFK	EKNINIVGDFK	
LQSLQTYVTQQLIR	ELGVVHNQDVNLHSSR	ELGVVHNQDVNLHSSR	
ALTGISVEQDKNTQEVFAQVK	ELLQNGMNGR	ELLQNGMNGR	
FLPFQQFGR	ELLVYAADPAMHAASGNLLDKR	ELLVYAADPAMHAASGNLLDKR	
HWPQIAQFAPSASAFFGMSRICMEVTPSGT	ELYHYQECVR	ELYHYQECVR	
SFIEDLLFNK	EMLAHAEETR	EMLAHAEETR	
TALTQHGKEDLK	EMLAHAEETRK	EMLAHAEETRK	
AGNGGDAALALLLDRLNQLESK	ENDSKEGFFTYICGFIQK	ENDSKEGFFTYICGFIQK	
YWPQIAQFAPSASAFF	ENSYTTTIKPVYK	ENSYTTTIKPVYK	
VYSTGNSVFNQTR	EPCSSGTYEGNSPFHPLADNK	EPCSSGTYEGNSPFHPLADNK	
DQVILLNK	EQIDGYVMHANYIFWR	EQIDGYVMHANYIFWR	
TLVATAEAEELAK	ESPFELEDFIPMDSTVK	ESPFELEDFIPMDSTVK	
GFQPTNGVGYQPYR	ESVQTFFK	ESVQTFFK	
FTALTQHKG	ETLYCIDGALLTK	ETLYCIDGALLTK	
AGNGGDAALALLLDR	ETMSYLFQHANLDSCK	ETMSYLFQHANLDSCK	
ALTGIAVEQDKNTQEVFAQVK	ETMSYLFQHANLDSCRK	ETMSYLFQHANLDSCRK	
FDNPVLPFNDGVYFSATEK	EVGFVVPGLPGTILR	EVGFVVPGLPGTILR	
GPEQTQGNFGDQELLR	FADDLNQLTGYK	FADDLNQLTGYK	
GWLFGTTLDSK	FADDLNQLTGYKKPASR	FADDLNQLTGYKKPASR	
ITFGGSDSTGSNENGER	FALTCFSTQFAFACPDGVK	FALTCFSTQFAFACPDGVK	
LDDKDPNFKDQVLLNK	FAPSASAFFGMSR	FAPSASAFFGMSR	
LQDLSSTASALGK	FASVYAWNR	FASVYAWNR	
MAGDGGDAALALLLDR	FCLEASFNYLK	FCLEASFNYLK	
NPANNAALVLQLPQGTTLPK	FDEDDSEPVK	FDEDDSEPVK	
RGPEQTQGNFGDEELIR	FDEDDSEPVKLG	FDEDDSEPVKLG	
RGPEQTQGNFGDQELLR	FDEDDSEPVKGVK	FDEDDSEPVKGVK	
SDNGPQNQRDAPR	FDNPVLPFNDGVYFASTEK	FDNPVLPFNDGVYFASTEK	
SFLEDLLFNK	FDTFNGECPNFVFLNSIIK	FDTFNGECPNFVFLNSIIK	
DDQIGYYR	FGDQELIR	FGDQELIR	

DDQIGYYRR	FGGPSDSTGSNQNGER	FGGPSDSTGSNQNGER	
DGILWVATEGALNTPKDHIGTR	FISTCACEIVGGQIVTCAK	FISTCACEIVGGQIVTCAK	
GIYQTSNFR	FKEGVEFLR	FKEGVEFLR	
GQGVPIINTNSSR	FKESPFLEDFIPMDSTVK	FKESPFLEDFIPMDSTVK	
GQGVPIINTNSSRDDQIGYYR	FKTEGLCVDIPGIPK	FKTEGLCVDIPGIPK	
LQEVVNQNAQALNTLVK	FLALCADSIIIGGAK	FLALCADSIIIGGAK	
NPANNAIIVLQLPEGTTLPK	FLPFQQFGR	FLPFQQFGR	
NSSRNSTPGSSIRTSPGMAGNGGDAALALLLLDR	FNFNGLTGTGVLTESNK	FNFNGLTGTGVLTESNK	
WYFYLLGTGPESGLPYGANK	FNGIGVTQNVLYENQK	FNGIGVTQNVLYENQK	
PGNGCDAALALLLLDR	FNGLTGTGVLTESNK	FNGLTGTGVLTESNK	
YLGTPESGLPYGANK	FNGLTVLPPLTD	FNGLTVLPPLTD	
PNFKDQVILLNK	FNPPALQDAYYR	FNPPALQDAYYR	
TALTQHKGEDLKFPR	FPNITNLCPFGEVFNATR	FPNITNLCPFGEVFNATR	
NPANNAIIVL	FQEKDEDDNLIDSYFVVK	FQEKDEDDNLIDSYFVVK	
QQTVTLLPAADLDYFSK	FQPTNGVGYQPYPYR	FQPTNGVGYQPYPYR	
RGPEQTQGNFGDQEL	FQTLALHR	FQTLALHR	
NPANDAAIIVLQLPQGTTLPK	FTALTQH GK	FTALTQH GK	
GTGPEAGLPYGANK	FTALTQHKGEDLK	FTALTQHKGEDLK	
DRLNQLESK	FTALTQHKGEDLKFPR	FTALTQHKGEDLKFPR	
TQHKGEDLKFPR	FTTTLNDFNLVAMK	FTTTLNDFNLVAMK	
ANNAIIVLQLPQGTTLPK	FVLALLSDLQDLK	FVLALLSDLQDLK	
AYNVTQAFGGR	FVSLAIDAYPLTK	FVSLAIDAYPLTK	
GPEQTQGNFGDQELIRR	FYDAQPCSDK	FYDAQPCSDK	
GQGVPIIDTNSPDDQIGYYR	GAGGHSYGADLK	GAGGHSYGADLK	
KQLTVTLLPAADLDDFSK	GANKDGIWVATEGALNTPK	GANKDGIWVATEGALNTPK	
LVDPQIQLAVTR	GAWNIGEQK	GAWNIGEQK	
MAGNGDAALALLLLDR	GCCSCGSCCKFDEDDSEPVLK	GCCSCGSCCKFDEDDSEPVLK	
NSSRTSTPGSSK	GDAALALLLLDR	GDAALALLLLDR	
QLTVTLLPAADLDDFSK	GDYGDVAVYR	GDYGDVAVYR	
DLPIEITVATSRTLSYYK	GEDIQLLK	GEDIQLLK	
GEGVPINTNSPDDQIGYYR	GFGDSVEEVLSEAR	GFGDSVEEVLSEAR	
LLPAADLDDFFK	GFQPTNGVGYQPYPYR	GFQPTNGVGYQPYPYR	
MAGDAALALL	GFYAEGSR	GFYAEGSR	
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NPANNAIIVLQIPQGTTLPK	GFYAEGSRGG	GFYAEGSRGG	
NSIPGSSMGTSPARMA	GFYAEGSRGGSQA	GFYAEGSRGGSQA	
NSTPGSSKPTSPARMAGNGGDAA	GFYAEGSRGGSQAS	GFYAEGSRGGSQAS	

SDNGPQNLPNAPR	GFYAEGSRGGSQASSR	GFYAEGSRGGSQASSR	
SILSPLYAFASEAAR	GGDAALALLLLDR	GGDAALALLLLDR	
SLVPGFNEK	GGDAALALLLLDRLNQLESK	GGDAALALLLLDRLNQLESK	
SLNVAKSEFDRDAAMQR	GGDGKMKDLSPR	GGDGKMKDLSPR	
IGAGICASYQTQTNspr	GGSYTNDKACPLIAAVITR	GGSYTNDKACPLIAAVITR	
NLNESLIDLQVL	GHFDDGQQGEVPVSIINNTVYTK	GHFDDGQQGEVPVSIINNTVYTK	
NSTPGSSMGTSpar	GIGVTQNVLYENQK	GIGVTQNVLYENQK	
AYETQALPQR	GIIWVATEGALNTPK	GIIWVATEGALNTPK	
KAYETQALPQR	GIYQTSNFR	GIYQTSNFR	
LNQLGSKMSG	GLPNNTASWFTALTQHGK	GLPNNTASWFTALTQHGK	
NGIIWVATEGALNTPK	GLPWNVVR	GLPWNVVR	
LNQLESKMAGK	GLTGTGVLTESNK	GLTGTGVLTESNK	
LGSPLSLNMAR	GMVLGSLAATVR	GMVLGSLAATVR	
AFQLTPIAVQMTK	GNGGDAALALLLLDR	GNGGDAALALLLLDR	
ITFGGSDSTGSNQNGGAR	GPEQTQGNFGDQELIR	GPEQTQGNFGDQELIR	
RATRRIPGGDGK	GPHEFCSQHTMLVK	GPHEFCSQHTMLVK	
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ITFGGSDSTGSNQNGQR	GPITDVFYKENSYTTTIKPVYTK	GPITDVFYKENSYTTTIKPVYTK	
LNKVEAEVQIDR	GQGVPIINTNSSPDDQIGY	GQGVPIINTNSSPDDQIGY	
	GQGVPIINTNSSPDDQIGYY	GQGVPIINTNSSPDDQIGYY	
	GQGVPIINTNSSPDDQIGYYR	GQGVPIINTNSSPDDQIGYYR	
	GQGVPIINTNSSPDDQIGYYRR	GQGVPIINTNSSPDDQIGYYRR	
	GQGVPIINTNSSPDDQIGYYRRATR	GQGVPIINTNSSPDDQIGYYRRATR	
	GQQQQGQTVTK	GQQQQGQTVTK	
	GQQQQGQTVTKK	GQQQQGQTVTKK	
	GQQQQGQTVTKKSAAEASK	GQQQQGQTVTKKSAAEASK	
	GQQQQGQTVTKKSAAEASKKPR	GQQQQGQTVTKKSAAEASKKPR	
	GSLPINVIVFDGK	GSLPINVIVFDGK	
	GTGPEAGLPYGANK	GTGPEAGLPYGANK	
	GTLEPEYFNSVCR	GTLEPEYFNSVCR	
	GTTVLLKEPCSSGTYEGNSPFHPLADNK	GTTVLLKEPCSSGTYEGNSPFHPLADNK	
	GVAPGTAVLR	GVAPGTAVLR	
	GVEAVMYMGTLSEYQFK	GVEAVMYMGTLSEYQFK	
	GVEAVMYMGTLSEYQFKK	GVEAVMYMGTLSEYQFKK	
	GVITHDVSSAINRPQIGVVR	GVITHDVSSAINRPQIGVVR	
	GVLPLQLEQPYVFIK	GVLPLQLEQPYVFIK	
	GVLPLQLEQPYVFIKR	GVLPLQLEQPYVFIKR	

	GVQIPCTCGK	GVQIPCTCGK	
	GVVFLHVTVVPAQEK	GVVFLHVTVVPAQEK	
	GVYFASTEK	GVYFASTEK	
	GVYYPDK	GVYYPDK	
	GVYYPDKVFR	GVYYPDKVFR	
	GWIFGTTLDSK	GWIFGTTLDSK	
	GYHLMSFPQSAPH	GYHLMSFPQSAPH	
	GYHLMSFPQSAPHGVVFLHVTVVPAQEK	GYHLMSFPQSAPHGVVFLHVTVVPAQEK	
	HADFDTWFSQR	HADFDTWFSQR	
	HCLHVVGPNVNK	HCLHVVGPNVNK	
	HCLHVVGPNVNKGEDIQLLK	HCLHVVGPNVNKGEDIQLLK	
	HFDEGNCDTLK	HFDEGNCDTLK	
	HGGGVAGALNK	HGGGVAGALNK	
	HGTFTCASEYTGNYQCGHYK	HGTFTCASEYTGNYQCGHYK	
	HIDAYKTFPPTPEK	HIDAYKTFPPTPEK	
	HLSHSHFVNLDNLR	HLSHSHFVNLDNLR	
	HTDFSSEIIGYK	HTDFSSEIIGYK	
	HTFSNYQHEETIYNLLK	HTFSNYQHEETIYNLLK	
	HTPINLVR	HTPINLVR	
	HVICTSEDMLNPNYEDLLIR	HVICTSEDMLNPNYEDLLIR	
	HVICTSEDMLNPNYEDLLIRK	HVICTSEDMLNPNYEDLLIRK	
	HWPQIAQF	HWPQIAQF	
	HWPQIAQFAPSASAF	HWPQIAQFAPSASAF	
	HWPQIAQFAPSASAFF	HWPQIAQFAPSASAFF	
	HWPQIAQFAPSASAFFGM	HWPQIAQFAPSASAFFGM	
	HWPQIAQFAPSASAFFGMSR	HWPQIAQFAPSASAFFGMSR	
	HYVYIGDPAQLPAPR	HYVYIGDPAQLPAPR	
	IADYNYK	IADYNYK	
	IADYNYKLPDDFTGCVIAWNSNNLDSK	IADYNYKLPDDFTGCVIAWNSNNLDSK	
	IAEIPKEEVKPFITESKPSVEQR	IAEIPKEEVKPFITESKPSVEQR	
	IAGHHLGR	IAGHHLGR	
	IAQFAPSASAFFGMSR	IAQFAPSASAFFGMSR	
	IFTIGTVTLK	IFTIGTVTLK	
	IFVDGVPFVSTGYHFR	IFVDGVPFVSTGYHFR	
	IGMEVTPSGTWLTY	IGMEVTPSGTWLTY	
	IGMEVTPSGTWLTYTGAIK	IGMEVTPSGTWLTYTGAIK	
	IGMEVTPSGTWLTYTGAIKLDDKDPNFK	IGMEVTPSGTWLTYTGAIKLDDKDPNFK	

	IGMEVTPSGTWLTYTGAIKLDDKDPNFKDQVILLNK	IGMEVTPSGTWLTYTGAIKLDDKDPNFKDQVILLNK	
	IGNYKLNTDHSSSSDNIALLVQ	IGNYKLNTDHSSSSDNIALLVQ	
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	IMASLVLAR	IMASLVLAR	
	IMTWLDMVDTSLSGFK	IMTWLDMVDTSLSGFK	
	IQDLSSTASALGK	IQDLSSTASALGK	
	IQEGVVDYGAR	IQEGVVDYGAR	
	IRGGDGKMKDLSPR	IRGGDGKMKDLSPR	
	ISEMHPALR	ISEMHPALR	
	ISNCVADYSVLYNSASFSTFK	ISNCVADYSVLYNSASFSTFK	
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	ITEHSWNADLYK	ITEHSWNADLYK	
	ITFGGPDSTGSNQNGER	ITFGGPDSTGSNQNGER	
	ITFGGPDSTGSNQNGERSGAR	ITFGGPDSTGSNQNGERSGAR	
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	IVDEPEEHVQIHTI	IVDEPEEHVQIHTI	
	IVDEPEEHVQIHTID	IVDEPEEHVQIHTID	
	IVDEPEEHVQIHTIDG	IVDEPEEHVQIHTIDG	
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	IVITSGDGTTSPISEHDYQIGGYTEK	IVITSGDGTTSPISEHDYQIGGYTEK	
	IVLQLPQGTTLPK	IVLQLPQGTTLPK	
	IVQLSEISMDNSPNLAWPLIVTALR	IVQLSEISMDNSPNLAWPLIVTALR	
	IVYTACSHAARDALCEK	IVYTACSHAARDALCEK	
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	IYCPACHNSEVGPESLAEYHNESGLK	IYCPACHNSEVGPESLAEYHNESGLK	
	IYSKHTPINLVR	IYSKHTPINLVR	
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	KADETQALPQRQRQ	KADETQALPQRQRQ	
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	NADIVEEAKK	NADIVEEAKK	
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	NGVLITEGSVK	NGVLITEGSVK	
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	NNELSPVALR	NNELSPVALR	
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	NVIPTITQMNLK	NVIPTITQMNLK	
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	SAGFPFNK	SAGFPFNK	
	SALEPLVDLPIGINITR	SALEPLVDLPIGINITR	
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	SDVLLPLTQYNR	SDVLLPLTQYNR	
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	WYFYLLGTGPEASLPYGANK	WYFYLLGTGPEASLPYGANK	
	YCALAPNMMVTNNTFTLK	YCALAPNMMVTNNTFTLK	
	YFSGAMDTTSYR	YFSGAMDTTSYR	
	YLTGPEAGLPYGANK	YLTGPEAGLPYGANK	
	YLQQESPFPVMSAPPAQYELK	YLQQESPFPVMSAPPAQYELK	
	YMNSQGLLPPK	YMNSQGLLPPK	
	YMSALNHTK	YMSALNHTK	
	YNENGTITDAVDCALDPLSETK	YNENGTITDAVDCALDPLSETK	
	YNLPTMCDIR	YNLPTMCDIR	
	YNSASFSTFK	YNSASFSTFK	

	YPANSIVCR	YPANSIVCR	
	YPQVNLTSIK	YPQVNLTSIK	
	YSQLDEEQPMEID	YSQLDEEQPMEID	
	YSTLQGPPGTGK	YSTLQGPPGTGK	
	YTMADLVYALR	YTMADLVYALR	
	YTQLCQYLNTLTLAVPYNMR	YTQLCQYLNTLTLAVPYNMR	
	YVDNNFCGPDGYPLECIK	YVDNNFCGPDGYPLECIK	
	YVDNNFCGPDGYPLECIKDLLAR	YVDNNFCGPDGYPLECIKDLLAR	
	YVLMDGSIQFPNTYLEGSR	YVLMDGSIQFPNTYLEGSR	
	YVQIPTTCANDPVGFTLK	YVQIPTTCANDPVGFTLK	
	YYLGTGPEAGLPYGANK	YYLGTGPEAGLPYGANK	
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	AIASEFSSLPSYAAFATAQEAYEQAVANGDSEVVL	AIASEFSSLPSYAAFATAQEAYEQAVANGDSEVVLK	
	ALTGIAVEQDKNTQEVFAQVKQIYK	ALTGIAVEQDKNTQEVFAQVKQIYK	
	AMPNMLR	AMPNMLR	
	ATYKPNTWCIR	ATYKPNTWCIR	
	AWIGFDVEGCHATR	AWIGFDVEGCHATR	
	AYKIEELFYSYATHSDK	AYKIEELFYSYATHSDK	
	CAYWVPR	CAYWVPR	
	CEESSAKSASVYYSQLMCQPILLDDQALVSDVGDSE	CEESSAKSASVYYSQLMCQPILLDDQALVSDVGDSEAEVAVK	
	CSAYTVELGTEVNEFACVADAVIK	CSAYTVELGTEVNEFACVADAVIK	
	CVPQADVEWK	CVPQADVEWK	
	CYGVSPKLNLDLCFTNVYADSFVIR	CYGVSPKLNLDLCFTNVYADSFVIR	
	CYGVSPKLNLDLCFTNVYADSFVIRGDEV	CYGVSPKLNLDLCFTNVYADSFVIRGDEV	
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	DEDDNLIDSYFVVK	DEDDNLIDSYFVVK	
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	DLSLQFK	DLSLQFK	
	DTTEAFEK	DTTEAFEK	
	DVLECNVK	DVLECNVK	
	DWSYSGQSTQLGIEFLKR	DWSYSGQSTQLGIEFLKR	
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	EDLKFP	EDLKFP	
	EETGLLMPLK	EETGLLMPLK	
	EGQINDMILSLLSKGR	EGQINDMILSLLSKGR	
	EGVEFLR	EGVEFLR	
	EIKESVQTFFK	EIKESVQTFFK	

	EILVTYNCCDDDYFNK	EILVTYNCCDDDYFNK	
	EILVTYNCCDDDYFNKK	EILVTYNCCDDDYFNKK	
	ELHLSWEVGKPRPPLNR	ELHLSWEVGKPRPPLNR	
	ELLVYAADPAMHAASGNLLLDK	ELLVYAADPAMHAASGNLLLDK	
	FASVYAWNPK	FASVYAWNPK	
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	FNVAITR	FNVAITR	
	FPVLHDIGNPK	FPVLHDIGNPK	
	FRIDGDMVPHISR	FRIDGDMVPHISR	
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	FTDGVCLFWNCNVDRYPANSIVCR	FTDGVCLFWNCNVDRYPANSIVCR	
	FVTDTPK	FVTDTPK	
	FYFYTSK	FYFYTSK	
	FYGGWHNMLK	FYGGWHNMLK	
	GATVVGTSK	GATVVGTSK	
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	IDGDMVPHISR	IDGDMVPHISR	
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	IEELFYSYATHSDKFTDGVCLFWNCNVDR	IEELFYSYATHSDKFTDGVCLFWNCNVDR	
	IKIVQMLSDTLK	IKIVQMLSDTLK	
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	ILNNLGVDIAANTVIWDYKR	ILNNLGVDIAANTVIWDYKR	
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	KFLPFQQFGR	KFLPFQQFGR	
	KGAWNIGEQQ	KGAWNIGEQQ	
	KLDGFMGR	KLDGFMGR	
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	LALGGSVAIK	LALGGSVAIK	
	LDGFMGR	LDGFMGR	
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	LFAAETLK	LFAAETLK	
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	LISMMGFK	LISMMGFK	
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	LYYDSMSYEDQDALFAYTKR	LYYDSMSYEDQDALFAYTKR	
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	NLQEFKPR	NLQEFKPR	
	NRDVTDFVNEFYAYLR	NRDVTDFVNEFYAYLR	
	NSIDAFK	NSIDAFK	
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	RISNCVADYSVLYNSASFSTFK	RISNCVADYSVLYNSASFSTFK	
	RLISMMGFK	RLISMMGFK	
	RNIKPVEVK	RNIKPVEVK	
	RNVIPTITQMNLK	RNVIPTITQMNLK	
	RSFIEDLLFNKVTLADAGFIK	RSFIEDLLFNKVTLADAGFIK	
	RSFYVYANGGK	RSFYVYANGGK	
	RVDWTIEYPIIGDELK	RVDWTIEYPIIGDELK	
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	SDGTGTIYTELEPPCR	SDGTGTIYTELEPPCR	
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	SHFAIGLALYPSAR	SHFAIGLALYPSAR	
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	TQFNYYK	TQFNYYK	
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	VGILCIMSDR	VGILCIMSDR	
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	VITGLHPTQAPTHLSVDTK	VITGLHPTQAPTHLSVDTK	
	VLSNLNLPGCDGGSLYVNK	VLSNLNLPGCDGGSLYVNK	
	VSAKPPPGDQFK	VSAKPPPGDQFK	
	VTIDYTEISFMLWCK	VTIDYTEISFMLWCK	
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	VVISDVLVNN	VVISDVLVNN	
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	VWTLMNVLTLVYK	VWTLMNVLTLVYK	
	VYPIILR	VYPIILR	
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